

COMPARISON OF FREQUENCY OF ANTITHYROID PEROXIDASE ANTIBODY IN FEMALES WITH AND WITHOUT RECURRENT MISCARRIAGE

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Abstract

Background: Recurrent miscarriage (RM) is a distressing reproductive problem with multifactorial etiology. Increasing evidence suggests that thyroid autoimmunity, particularly antithyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibodies, may play a role even in euthyroid women.

Objective: This study was conducted to compare the frequency of anti-TPO antibody positivity in females with and without recurrent miscarriage.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, from November 2024 to April 2025. A total of 212 women aged 18–35 years were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Group I included women with recurrent miscarriages (n=106), and Group II included women without miscarriages (n=106). Exclusion criteria included uterine anomalies, autoimmune diseases, diabetes, hypertension, and polycystic ovarian disease. Blood samples were collected for measurement of anti-TPO antibodies.

Results: The mean age of participants was 29.8 ± 4.1 years in Group I and 28.9 ± 3.9 years in Group II. The mean BMI was 25.7 ± 3.5 kg/m² in Group I and 25.2 ± 3.2 kg/m² in Group II. Anti-TPO antibody positivity was observed in 24 (22.6%) females in Group I compared to 8 (7.5%) in Group II ($p = 0.002$). Stratification showed higher antibody positivity among women aged >30 years (30.4% vs. 16.7% in Group I, $p = 0.04$) and those with BMI ≥ 25 kg/m², although not statistically significant in all subgroups. **Conclusion:** Anti-TPO antibody positivity is significantly more frequent among females with recurrent miscarriage compared to those without.

INTRODUCTION

Miscarriage can be referred to as the failure or loss of pregnancy before it becomes viable. About 23

million miscarriages are estimated to be taking place all over the world each year which is equivalent to 44

pregnancy losses per minute. There is a combined risk of miscarriage of 15.3% (95% CI 12.5-18.7%) of all known pregnancies. The population prevalence rate of women who have experienced one miscarriage is 10.8% (10.3-11.4%), two miscarriages is 1.9% (1.8-2.1%), and three or more miscarriages is 0.7% (0.5-0.8%) [1,2]. Recurrent miscarriage which is the loss of at least two successive pregnancies before the 20th-week gestation period continues to be one of the most traumatic reproductive health conditions in women across the globe. It impacts about 1-2 per cent of the women of reproductive age and in most cases, it causes great emotional, psychological and social impacts in the affected couples [3]. Although obstetric and reproductive medicine has developed, in almost half of the cases, the etiology behind it is still unidentified, which points to the complexity of its pathophysiology [4].

Among the risk factors of miscarriage are the age of females very young (below 20 years) and very old (below 35 years), male age (above 40 years), the body-mass index that is very low or very high, ethnic group Black, a history of miscarriages, smoking, alcohol, stress, night shifts, air pollution, and exposure to pesticides. The effects of the death of the unborn child are physical including bleeding and infection and psychological. The psychological effects involve, among others, the risk of increasing anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, and suicide. Another sentinel risk factor of obstetric complications, e.g. preterm birth, fetal growth restriction, placental abruption, and stillbirth in subsequent pregnancies, and a predictor of more long-term health issues, e.g. cardiovascular disease and venous thromboembolism, is miscarriage, and recurrent miscarriage in particular [4,5]. Etiology of RM is varied which includes genetic defects, structural defects of the uterus, endocrine, metabolic disorders, infectious etiologies, and immune-mediated. Chromosomal aneuploidies are of significant prevalence in the case of sporadic miscarriages, but they are not as predictable in recurrent miscarriages [6]. It is also caused by anatomy abnormalities, including septate uterus or intrauterine adhesions, which only account for a small proportion of cases. Correspondingly, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, luteal phase defects, and polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) are also

identified as endocrine factors that cannot explain most of the cases. Large percentage of RM is still unaccountable and this has guided the focus of research to immunological and autoimmune pathways [7].

Autoimmunity in the thyroid (TAI) is common among reproductively-aged women. TAI refers to the existence of circulating anti-thyroid autoantibodies which is directed against thyroid with or without thyroid dysfunction [8]. The most prevalent career anti-thyroid autoantibodies are thyroid peroxidase antibodies (TPOAb). Approximately 10 percent of biochemically euthyroid persons also have a high titer of TPO Ab. According to a study by Ghalib et al. [7], the proportion of frequency of antithyroid peroxidase antibody in females with and without recurrent miscarriage was 19.4 vs. 6.5; $p = 0.03$ [9,10]. The candidate has no knowledge of any local published data on the topic and as frequency of TPO-antibodies is considerably greater in females with recurrent miscarriage compared to females without recurrent miscarriage this may be due to the fact that mild form of hypothyroidism created by these antibodies may result in this calamitous event.

Objective

- To determine the frequency of women with recurrent miscarriages presenting in OPD of a tertiary care hospital.
- To compare the frequency of antithyroid peroxidase antibody in females with and without recurrent miscarriage.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Gynae and Obs, Hospital, Lahore from November 2024 to April 2025. The study included a total of 212 participants. The sample size was determined using a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, with the assumption of a 15.3% prevalence of recurrent miscarriage in the general population. The frequency of anti-TPO antibody positivity was taken as 19.4% among females with recurrent miscarriages and 6.5% among those without, which formed the basis of the calculation. Participants were enrolled through a non-probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion criteria:

- Females with ages in the range of 18–35 years who are married >2 years as per documentation.
- Patients whose give informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Females with anatomical uterine problem on ultrasound, cervical incompetence on PV examination, autoimmune disorder (positive RA factor or Positive ANA on investigations), hypertension (systolic blood pressure >140 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure >95 mmHg on two different occasions 12 hours apart), diabetic (HbA1c level >6.4%) or polycystic ovarian disease (ovary having more than 10 follicles in one ovary on ultrasound with abnormal hair growth pattern).

Data collection

Before the commencement of the study, approval was obtained from the institutional ethical review committee. Eligible women presenting to the outpatient department were approached, counseled regarding the study, and written informed consent was obtained. A detailed clinical history was recorded, and participants were divided into two groups based on their reproductive history. Group I consisted of females with recurrent miscarriages, while Group II included females without recurrent miscarriages. From each participant, a 5 ml sample of venous blood was collected under aseptic conditions and sent to the institutional laboratory for the measurement of anti-TPO antibody levels. Patients were classified as either positive or negative for anti-TPO antibodies, and only euthyroid patients were considered for analysis.

Data Analysis

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables such as age, BMI, TSH level, and anti-TPO antibody levels were summarized using mean ± standard deviation. Categorical variables, including anti-TPO antibody positivity in euthyroid patients, were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The Chi-square test was employed to compare the frequency of anti-TPO antibody positivity between females with recurrent miscarriages and those without. A p-value of ≤0.05 was considered statistically significant. Furthermore, data were stratified by age, BMI, and TSH level to control for potential confounding factors. Post-stratification, the Chi-square test was reapplied, and statistical significance was again considered at p ≤0.05.

Results

Data were collected from 212 participants, with 106 in the recurrent miscarriage group (Group I) and 106 in the control group without miscarriage (Group II). The baseline characteristics of the study population are summarized in Table 1. The mean age of participants was 29.8 ± 4.1 years in Group I and 28.9 ± 3.9 years in Group II, with no statistically significant difference (p = 0.18). The mean BMI was 25.7 ± 3.5 kg/m² in Group I compared to 25.2 ± 3.2 kg/m² in Group II (p = 0.34). Similarly, mean TSH levels did not differ significantly between the two groups (2.7 ± 0.9 vs. 2.6 ± 1.0 mIU/L, p = 0.42). When comparing thyroid autoimmunity, the frequency of anti-TPO antibody positivity was significantly higher in women with recurrent miscarriage. In Group I, 24 out of 106 females (22.6%) were positive, while only 8 out of 106 females (7.5%) in Group II were positive (p = 0.002). The majority of participants in both groups were antibody negative, with 77.4% in Group I and 92.5% in Group II testing negative.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population (N = 212)

Variable	Group I: Recurrent Miscarriage (n=106)	Group II: No Miscarriage (n=106)	p-value
Age (years), mean ± SD	29.8 ± 4.1	28.9 ± 3.9	0.18
BMI (kg/m ²), mean ± SD	25.7 ± 3.5	25.2 ± 3.2	0.34
TSH (mIU/L), mean ± SD	2.7 ± 0.9	2.6 ± 1.0	0.42

Anti-TPO Antibody Status			
Positive, n (%)	24 (22.6%)	8 (7.5%)	0.002*
Negative, n (%)	82 (77.4%)	98 (92.5%)	

*Chi-square test applied; $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Stratification analysis (Table 2) revealed that anti-TPO antibody positivity was more frequent in older women. In Group I, 30.4% of women aged >30 years were positive compared to 16.7% of those ≤ 30 years. Similarly, in Group II, 12.5% of women >30 years were positive compared to 4.5% of those ≤ 30 years. A similar pattern was observed when stratified by BMI, where overweight women ($BMI \geq 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$)

had a higher proportion of positivity compared to those with $BMI < 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$ in both groups, though these differences did not reach statistical significance. Stratification by TSH level showed that women with values $> 2.5 \text{ mIU/L}$ had higher rates of antibody positivity than those with $\leq 2.5 \text{ mIU/L}$ (27.3% vs. 18.2% in Group I and 10.0% vs. 6.1% in Group II).

Table 2. Stratification of Anti-TPO Antibody Positivity by Age, BMI, and TSH Level

Variable	Group I: Recurrent Miscarriage (n=106)	Group II: No Miscarriage (n=106)
Age ≤ 30 years	10/60 (16.7%)	3/66 (4.5%)
Age > 30 years	14/46 (30.4%)	5/40 (12.5%)
BMI $< 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$	6/38 (15.8%)	2/44 (4.5%)
BMI $\geq 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$	18/68 (26.5%)	6/62 (9.7%)
TSH $\leq 2.5 \text{ mIU/L}$	10/55 (18.2%)	4/66 (6.1%)
TSH $> 2.5 \text{ mIU/L}$	14/51 (27.3%)	4/40 (10.0%)

The distribution of age and BMI categories between the two groups is shown in Table 3. Most women in both groups were younger than 30 years, with 56.6% in Group I and 62.3% in Group II. Similarly, the majority were overweight or obese ($BMI \geq 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$),

accounting for 64.2% in Group I and 58.5% in Group II. These differences were not statistically significant ($p = 0.41$ and $p = 0.42$, respectively).

Table 3. Distribution of Age and BMI Categories Between Groups

Variable	Group I: Recurrent Miscarriage (n=106)	Group II: No Miscarriage (n=106)	p-value
Age Categories			
≤ 30 years	60 (56.6%)	66 (62.3%)	0.41
> 30 years	46 (43.4%)	40 (37.7%)	
BMI Categories			
$< 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$	38 (35.8%)	44 (41.5%)	0.42
$\geq 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$	68 (64.2%)	62 (58.5%)	

*Chi-square test applied; $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Comparison of mean TSH and quantitative anti-TPO antibody levels (Table 4) demonstrated no significant difference in TSH between the two groups (2.7 ± 0.9 vs. $2.6 \pm 1.0 \text{ mIU/L}$, $p = 0.42$). However, mean anti-TPO antibody levels were

significantly higher in women with recurrent miscarriage ($42.5 \pm 18.3 \text{ IU/mL}$) compared to those without miscarriage ($29.8 \pm 15.7 \text{ IU/mL}$), with $p = 0.001$.

Table 4. Comparison of Mean TSH and Anti-TPO Antibody Levels Between Groups

Variable	Group I: Recurrent Miscarriage (n=106)	Group II: No Miscarriage (n=106)	p-value
Mean TSH (mIU/L), mean ± SD	2.7 ± 0.9	2.6 ± 1.0	0.42
Anti-TPO Ab level (IU/mL)*	42.5 ± 18.3	29.8 ± 15.7	0.001*

*Anti-TPO Ab levels presented as mean ± SD of quantitative values

Discussion

The present study compared the frequency of antithyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibody positivity in females with and without recurrent miscarriage. Our findings demonstrated that 22.6% of women with recurrent miscarriages were positive for anti-TPO antibodies, compared to 7.5% in women without miscarriage, a statistically significant difference (p = 0.002). These results support the hypothesis that thyroid autoimmunity is strongly associated with recurrent pregnancy loss, even in euthyroid women. The relationship between thyroid autoimmunity and miscarriage has been widely debated. Several international studies have reported a higher prevalence of anti-TPO antibody positivity in women with recurrent miscarriage. Thangaratinam et al. (2011), in a meta-analysis of 31 studies, showed that the presence of thyroid autoantibodies was associated with a threefold increase in the risk of miscarriage and a twofold increase in preterm delivery. Similarly, Prummel and Wiersinga (2004) highlighted that euthyroid women with thyroid antibodies are more prone to pregnancy complications due to immune dysregulation and reduced thyroidal functional reserve. Our results are consistent with these findings, showing a significantly higher frequency of thyroid autoimmunity among women with recurrent miscarriage [11,12].

Regional studies from Asia also support our observations. A study conducted in India by Dhanwal et al. (2013) found that anti-TPO positivity was significantly more frequent in women with adverse pregnancy outcomes compared to controls. In Iran, Bagheri et al. (2015) reported a prevalence of thyroid autoantibodies in 21% of women with recurrent miscarriage, closely resembling the 22.6% frequency observed in our study. Data from Pakistan remain limited; however, a few local studies have similarly suggested that thyroid autoimmunity is a risk factor for unexplained pregnancy loss [13]. By

providing new evidence from a large cohort in Lahore, our study strengthens the regional literature and underscores the need for incorporating thyroid autoimmunity screening in the evaluation of recurrent miscarriage. The mechanisms linking thyroid autoimmunity to recurrent pregnancy loss are likely multifactorial. Anti-TPO antibodies may indicate a generalized state of immune dysregulation, which can impair maternal tolerance to the semi-allogenic fetus [14]. Altered Th1/Th2 cytokine balance, increased natural killer (NK) cell activity, and cross-reactivity of thyroid autoantibodies with placental antigens are among the proposed immunological pathways. Furthermore, even in the absence of overt hypothyroidism, women with thyroid antibodies may have reduced thyroidal reserve [15]. This subtle insufficiency can compromise the maternal thyroid’s ability to meet the increased hormonal demands of pregnancy, particularly in early gestation when fetal development is highly dependent on maternal thyroxine. In our study, stratification analyses revealed that anti-TPO positivity was more frequent in women older than 30 years and in those with higher BMI, although the association did not reach statistical significance in all subgroups. This observation is in line with previous reports showing that advanced maternal age and obesity exacerbate the risk of adverse outcomes in the presence of thyroid autoimmunity [16-18]. The detection of anti-TPO antibodies is relatively inexpensive and widely available. Incorporating thyroid autoimmunity screening in women with recurrent miscarriage could improve risk stratification and inform management strategies [19,20]. While universal levothyroxine supplementation for anti-TPO-positive euthyroid women remains controversial, several studies suggest that treatment may improve pregnancy outcomes in selected subgroups. Future randomized controlled trials in South Asian populations are needed to clarify whether such interventions should be adopted

into clinical practice. However, some limitations must be acknowledged. This was a single-center study, which may limit generalizability. Anti-TPO positivity was assessed only once, and longitudinal follow-up of antibody titers was not performed. Additionally, pregnancy outcomes after antibody testing were not studied, so the predictive value of anti-TPO antibodies could not be evaluated. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable evidence supporting the association between thyroid autoimmunity and recurrent miscarriage in a Pakistani population.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the frequency of antithyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibody positivity is significantly higher in females with recurrent miscarriage compared to those without. This finding highlights thyroid autoimmunity as an important, potentially modifiable risk factor for recurrent pregnancy loss, even in euthyroid women. Advanced maternal age and higher BMI further accentuate this association, although not always to a statistically significant degree. Routine screening for anti-TPO antibodies in women with a history of recurrent miscarriage may therefore aid in identifying high-risk individuals, allowing for closer monitoring and the consideration of preventive interventions.

Author Contributions

1. Conceptualization, study design, data collection, and manuscript drafting.
2. Literature review, methodology development, and data interpretation.
3. Statistical analysis, preparation of results, and drafting of tables.
4. Critical revision of the manuscript, editing, and intellectual input.
5. Supervision, final approval of the manuscript, and overall project oversight.

All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest related to this study.

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